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Prognostic Projection of Breast Cancer: Artificial Intelligence Modelling

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ABSTRACT

There is a dearth of breast cancer data in developing countries, especially Nigeria. This has made it difficult to make satisfactory population based inference with regards to prognosis of the disease. While it is known that the prognosis of breast cancer is generally bad and indeed worse among African women diagnosed, it is not known to what extent and what factors are more contributory than others. With unavailable data, it is difficult to use classical mathematical tools to make prognostic projections. An artificial intelligence modeling system – the fuzzy inference system – is adequate for data analysis in this situation.

The traditional factors that predict recurrence of the disease or death have been analyzed in many studies. This study analyzed four input variables (Age at diagnosis, Age, Stage, and Race) and one output variable (five year survival rate). Data used was from the National Cancer Institute. The rate of risk of attainment of each input variable expresses the output variable. A database was established. The prognosis (five year survival rate) of breast cancer can be made by varying the input data. This calculated result takes into account all uncertainties and inaccuracies related to the nature of the input variables.

Keywords: breast cancer, fuzzy inference system, intelligence modeling

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